
Procedia
**Environmental Science,
Engineering and Management**
<http://www.procedia-esem.eu>

Procedia Environmental Science, Engineering and Management **12** (2025) (4) 1285-1292

28th International Trade Fair of Material and Energy Recovery and Sustainable Development,
ECOMONDO, 4th-7th November, 2025, Rimini, Italy

SYMBA: ADVANCING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS FOR A SUSTAINABLE, CIRCULAR AND BIO-BASED EUROPE*

Antonietta Pizza^{1}, Marco de la Feld¹, Mirko Busto¹,
María Aralda Torres Serrano¹, Hector Leiva², Abdulaziz Aldureid³,
Lucía González-Monjardín⁴, Erica Locatelli⁵, Stefano Cisternino⁵**

¹*ENCO Srl, Via Michelangelo Schipa 115, 80122, Naples, Italy*

²*CIRCE, Parque Empresarial Dinamiza, Av. Ranillas, 3D, 1º, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain*

³*AIMPLAS, Carrer de Gustave Eiffel, 4, 46980 Paterna, Valencia, Spain*

⁴*CETAQUA, AquaHub-A Vila da Auga, Rúa José Villar Granjel 33, 15890 Santiago de Compostela, Spain*

⁵*ICLEI, Leopoldring 3, 79098 Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany*

Abstract

SYMBA is a Horizon Europe project that aims to reduce environmental impacts on soil, water, and air by promoting Industrial Symbiosis practices across multiple sectors and regions. The project involves nine partners across five EU countries. The core objective is to develop a replicable Industrial Symbiosis methodology tailored to specific industrial contexts. This methodology will integrate and adapt established sustainability assessment frameworks, Life Cycle Assessment, Social Life Cycle Assessment, and Life Cycle Costing, to address the complexity of IS networks. Although Life Cycle Assessment is commonly used in Industrial Symbiosis studies, existing models often fail to capture multi-level interactions across actors and resource flows. Evidence from past Industrial Symbiosis networks indicates significant potential for environmental and economic benefits, including emission reductions of up to 31% and cost savings of up to 30%. SYMBA's approach begins with a structured literature review to extract methodological insights. This informs a regional analysis conducted across four demonstration sites, selected for their high Industrial Symbiosis potential. The analysis assesses readiness levels, existing practices, and sector-specific challenges, enabling adaptation of the methodology to each local context. The project also addresses policy barriers through collaboration with regional stakeholders, co-creating a Policy and Strategy Roadmap to guide Industrial Symbiosis deployment at scale. Outcomes will include actionable recommendations, best practices, and scalable business models. By promoting the circular use of resources and integration of secondary raw materials, SYMBA aims to strengthen Europe's bio-based economy and industrial resilience while demonstrating the real-world viability of industrial symbiosis.

Keywords: bioeconomy, circularity, industrial symbiosis, waste reuse

*Selection and peer-review under responsibility of the ECOMONDO

** Corresponding author: email: pizza@enco-consulting.it, telephone: +39 0817611727

1. Introduction

The industrial sector holds an inestimable value as a driving force of the European (EU) economy. According to Eurostat, the largest industries in Europe include food, beverages, tobacco, motor vehicles and other transport equipment and metals. However, as the European Environmental Agency (EEA) indicates, the EU industries continue to affect the environment, climate, and public health by exerting pressure through atmospheric the environment in the form of emissions to atmosphere and ecosystems, waste generation and resource consumption. Against this backdrop, the concepts of circular economy, Industry 4.0 and industrial symbiosis (IS) have emerged and are increasingly interconnected. Together, they aim to respond to global challenges in the most effective and sustainable way. Within this context, IS, as an integral component circular economy, envisions the creation of ecosystems in which energy and material flows are optimized, waste is minimized, and by-products repurposed to create added value (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989).

The SYMBA project builds on this vision by seeking to accelerate the adoption of IS across Europe. Its main objective is to develop of comprehensive guidelines, introduce innovative multi-criteria decision-making tools, and implement pilot applications in selected regions. By combining methodological rigor with real world experimentation, the project aims to deliver practical pathways for scaling IS across diverse industrial contexts.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis Methodology to evaluate IS solutions

SYMBA comprises multiple methodological phases, each designed to achieve a distinct objective. The prioritization and analysis of collected data were conducted using a combination of co-creation decision method and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA).

For the assessment of IS solutions, the study employed a weighted-sum MCDA integrating life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) indicators (Belton and Stewart, 2002;), while the mapping of IS regions was performed using a criteria-based Geographic Information System (GIS) analysis combining regional industrial data, material flow information from the SYMBA database, and stakeholder input from ICLEI's network (Domenech et al., 2019).

2.2. The SYMBA Co-Creation Decision Method and Multi-criteria decision analysis

The Co-Creation Decision Method (CCDM) represents a participatory framework that actively integrates the diverse perspectives of stakeholders who contribute valuable to a service or product. This method facilitates collaborative development, evaluation, and selection of optimal solutions (Pralhad et al., 2004). In contrast to conventional top-down decision-making models, CCDM emphasizes shared ownership, inclusivity, and iterative feedback, thereby ensuring that the outcomes reflect the needs, expectations, and priorities of all involved actors. This approach is particularly advantageous in complex, multi-stakeholder contexts, such as public policy design, sustainable development initiatives, and innovation management where diverse and sometimes conflicting interests must be harmonized. In SYMBA, the CCDM was implemented twice by AIMPLAS and CETAQUA, utilizing different technological tools, including *Microsoft Outlook* and *Mentimeter*. The participants involved in the co-creation activities for the development of the CCMD include representatives from the consortium partners, as well as external stakeholders including 7 participants from industry, 7 participants from scientific community, 2 participants from government agencies, 1 participant from community and 3 listed as other. On the other hand, the MCDA acts as a key framework comprising both qualitative and quantitative methodologies

designed to facilitate decision-making processes involving multiple, often competing criteria. This approach provides systematic support for resolving complex problems where stakeholders must balance conflicting objectives and reach compromise solutions (Belton et al., 2002).

In SYMBA, the IS solutions were systematically evaluated across five readiness-level criteria: Symbiosis, Environmental, Societal, Organizational, and Legal/Ethical readiness. Each criterion was assigned an individual score based on predefined metrics. Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of the outcomes from both implementation rounds, including the selected readiness levels (Criteria) and their corresponding percentage distributions.

Table 1. Average weightings for the criteria generated in the two rounds (internal and external) and final weighting

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Internal weighting factor (%)</i>	<i>External weighting factor (%)</i>	<i>Final weighting factor (%)</i>
Symbiosis Readiness Levels (SymRL)	30	26.6	28
Environmental Readiness Levels (ERL)	25	18.4	22
Legal and ethical Readiness Level (LRL)	15	21.1	18
Organisational Readiness Level (ORL)	15	21.4	18
Societal Readiness Level (SRL)	15	11.6	14

When integrated with structured analytical tools such as MCDA, CCDM enhances the objectivity of the decision-making process by systematically evaluating and prioritizing criteria, while maintaining high levels of stakeholder engagement. The result is a comprehensive and context-sensitive methodology that effectively combines qualitative input with quantitative analysis.

2.3. Scalability and transferability of SYMBA

According to Bocken (2014), sustainable business models focus on the creation of new systems, which involves a wide range of stakeholders, instead of focusing on one single technology aspect. In order to support the implementation of sustainable business models, Bocken identified eight archetypes in which different sustainable models can be classified into depending on their objective: 1) maximize material and energy efficiency, 2) create value from waste, 3) substitute renewables and natural processes, 4) deliver functionality rather than ownership, 5) adopt a stewardship role, 6) encourage sufficiency, 7) re-purpose the business for society/environment, and 8) develop scale-up solutions. The business model canvas for SYMBA has been developed by the combination of three main elements:

- **Objective:** maximizing material and energy efficiency and/or creating value from waste
- **Baseline business model canvas:** Strategic Public-Private Innovation Network Business Model Canvas (SPIN BMC), developed by TNO, whose aim is to facilitate the building, scaling up and replicating of ecosystems of industrial symbiosis and circular economy (Fraccascia et al. 2019)
- **Potential governance models** (Schaltegger et al., 2012):
 - Model 1: Activities and responsibilities of members are based on a consortium agreement and benefits from the expertise of the members.
 - Model 3: Small group of people that constantly stimulates IS practices and attempts to discover unexploited IS opportunities.
 - Model 6: Coalition of several large private industrial companies that act as legal entities and have a shared interest in promoting the network’s success.

The SYMBA sustainability business model canvas for IS has been developed based on 9 building blocks: Key Partners, Key Activities, Key Resources, Value Proposition, Stakeholder Segment, Innovation Services, Impact and Sustainability metric, Cost-structure, Circular Innovation Portfolio. The SYMBA Business Model is scalable due to its modular block design,

which integrates aspects common to different value chains (partners, activities, resources, innovation services, cost structure) while placing an emphasis on where sustainability and innovation can occur. This structure enables the replication across multiple organizations and sectors. In addition, transferability is ensured through the application of the SYMBA Methodology offering sector-specific guidelines – for textile, packaging, waste, wastewater and agrifood – that can be adapted and replicated in other industrial ecosystems. In this way, the model combines standardized modules with flexible methodological guidance, making it applicable across diverse contexts and a robust tool to foster circular economy transitions.

2.4. SYMBA Methodology/Guidelines

To promote the adoption of IS, SYMBA is developing methodological guidelines for applying Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) within IS systems. These guidelines are created through a step-by-step process that integrates evidence from existing literature with practical testing in demonstration regions.

The process begins by drawing on ongoing methodological debates and accumulated experience in applying LCA, LCC, and s-LCA to industrial symbiosis. A combination of manual reviews of key IS studies with an AI-supported large-scale scans is used to identify recent trends and reveal existing gaps. By synthesizing these insights, methodological approaches and modelling choices are consolidated into a preliminary set of guidelines. This draft is then shared with SYMBA demonstration regions, where feedback on local needs, capacities, and sector specific challenges is collected. The inclusion of regional perspectives ensures that the guidelines are not only scientifically robust but also practical and relevant to the realities of diverse industrial contexts. The iterative validation process increases the reliability of the framework and encourages stakeholder ownership. Once refined, the guidelines are tested through selected case studies, serving as living laboratories for real-world implementation. These applications allow the project team to adjust and strengthen the methodology, ensuring it is adaptable to varying industrial settings and scalable across different regions. The lessons learned will provide the final version of the guidelines, creating a reference that can be applied widely to enhance sustainability assessments.

Ultimately, the development of these guidelines represents more than technical exercise. It reflects SYMBA's commitment to fostering systemic change by enabling industries to understand the environmental, social, and economic implications of their collaborative practices. By providing clear, evidence based, and context sensitive tools, the project aims to accelerate the transition toward a more circular and resilient European economy, where resources are used efficiently, and industrial networks contribute to broader sustainability goals.

3. Case-studies

Candidate regions were identified through outreach to ICLEI and partner networks, as well as through a public call for expressions of interest. An initial pre-screen applied four criteria: bio-based potential, geographic diversity, willingness to develop local value chains, and stakeholder commitment. The shortlisted regions were validated together with project partners, after which four demonstration sites were selected. Geographic information systems were then used to map industrial clusters, resource streams, and potential synergies in each site. This selection process aligns with European evidence on where IS tends to emerge and scale, as described in SYMBA's public communication (Domenech et al., 2019).

3.1. Presentation of case studies

Four case studies were ultimately selected as high-potential regions for IS within the SYMBA project. The selection process was structured and participatory, combining systematic

literature reviews with stakeholders' engagement to ensure both geographic diversity and strong bio-based potential. Based on criteria such as the presence of bio-based industries, opportunities for local value chain development, sectoral relevance, and commitment from regional actors the Metropolitan City of Milan (Italy), Murcia (Spain), Flanders (Belgium), and the island of Bornholm (Denmark) were chosen. Each offers a distinct context for testing SYMBA's IS methodology, highlighting diverse challenges, opportunities, and innovation pathways across Europe.

3.2. High potential IS regions identification

The identification of high potential IS regions in SYMBA followed a structured, multi-stage procedure designed to ensure both geographic diversity and the presence of enabling conditions for IS uptake. This process built on established European mapping approaches (Domenech et al., 2019) and adapted them to the project's bio-based focus and stakeholder-driven methodology.

3.2.1 Site selection criteria

ICLEI reached out to a pool of potential facilitators of IS and an open call for expressions of interest circulated through ICLEI's networks and SYMBA partner channels. Interested regions were screened against four pre-defined selection criteria:

1. **Bio-based potential** – availability of bio-based industries, agricultural and forestry activities, and related by-product streams suitable for symbiotic exchange.
2. **Geographic diversity** – representation of different EU macro-regions to test replicability under varying regulatory, infrastructural, and socio-economic contexts.
3. **Local value chain development potential** – evidence of existing industrial clusters or planned investments that could anchor symbiotic relationships.
4. **Stakeholder commitment** – demonstrated willingness of local authorities, companies, and other actors to participate in SYMBA activities.

The final selection of demonstration sites was validated collectively by project partners. This set reflects a balance of sectoral specialization, policy frameworks, and spatial characteristics, providing a robust basis for testing the scalability and transferability of the SYMBA methodology.

3.2.2. Sectoral and regional characteristics

- **CETENMA, Region of Murcia.** Focused on agri-food, biowaste and wastewater streams. Main barriers are regulatory complexity and funding access. Interest in regulatory support, financial incentives and digital matchmaking.
- **Gruppo CAP, Metropolitan City of Milan.** Advanced initiatives on PHA rich biomass for bioplastics, phosphorus rich biomass for fertilizers, biomethane for grid injection and cellulose recovery. Challenges include regulatory pathways, limited partners and logistics costs, with attention to End of Waste certification.
- **OVAM, Flanders.** Public authority developing a digital platform to map biomass supply and demand, clarify legislation and enable matchmaking. Obstacles include fragmented market knowledge, complex legislation and limited resources.
- **BOFA, Bornholm.** Early-stage context with priorities on plastics, food waste and textiles. Constraints include infrastructure and investment needs and precautionary approaches on treated wastewater. Mature composting for garden waste and participation in SYMSITES. The flagship idea is a multi-input multi-output biorefinery.

4. Results and discussion

Industrial Symbiosis remains only weakly embedded in European and national legislation. The Waste Framework Directive provides definitions for waste, by-products, and end-of-waste

criteria, yet it does not establish a clear pathway for material exchanges among firms. As a result, many potentially reusable streams are still classified as waste, creating additional related to permitting and cross-border shipment requirements. Comparative evidence across Europe indicates that policy instruments, incentives, and permitting practices differ widely between country and region. A large European review mapped network types, resources exchanges, and common obstacles. It highlighted how economic incentives and legislative complexity directly influence the scale-up of IS, particularly through administrative challenges associated with the movement of secondary materials across burdens (Domenech et al., 2019).

Recent contributions underscore the absence of explicit IS strategies in most policy planning documents. This body of work calls for regulatory innovation to reduce legal uncertainty and lower transaction costs for firms, thereby creating a more favorable environment for industrial collaboration (Cudecka-Purina, 2025). Building on this evidence, four practical policy lines can be proposed. First, it is essential to clarify and harmonize the distinction between waste and by-products, while expanding end-of-waste criteria to include relevant bio-based streams. Second, tailored economic incentives such as reduced waste fees and targeted tax relief for verified exchanges. Third, the development of reliable information infrastructure and open data platforms is crucial for effective matchmaking between companies. Public resources such as SYMBA's searchable database and user-friendly interface illustrate how accessible tools can significantly lower search and coordination costs for both companies and administrations. Finally, industrial symbiosis should be integrated into regional development strategies and cohesion programs. Transparent and criteria-based region selection, as demonstrated in the cases of the Metropolitan City of Milan, Region of Murcia, Flanders, and Bornholm (Domenech et al., 2019; SYMBA, 2025).

The first step of the methodological work focused on a manual literature review of seminal studies applying LCA and LCC to industrial symbiosis. One of the main challenges concerns the definition of reference scenarios. Studies consistently compare IS against counterfactual cases such as stand-alone production or sector averages. While these reference systems are necessary to quantify benefits, they vary in ambition and design, often leading to uncertainty in results (Mattila et al., 2012; Aissani et al., 2019; Zhu, 2013). The choice of reference is therefore central to guideline development, as it determines the robustness of claims regarding avoided impacts and cost savings.

A second recurring issue is multifunctionality, which arises from the multiple outputs of symbiotic networks. Approaches include system expansion (substitution), allocation rules based on mass, energy, or economic value, and hybrid combinations. Although system expansion is generally preferred for capturing avoided burdens, data gaps frequently force the use of allocation (Kerdlap et al., 2020; Sandin and Peters, 2018). This underscores the need for flexibility in the guidelines, with explicit rules for determining when each method is most appropriate. Defining system boundaries also emerge as a key methodological decision. Broad boundaries that capture upstream inputs and downstream effects, such as transport, collection, waste treatment, are recommended to avoid problem shifting. However, such extensions often increase data requirements (Sandin and Peters, 2018; Sokka et al., 2010). Hybrid models that combine process-based LCA with Input-Output analysis are proposed as a solution to bridge data gaps and include off-site effects (Dong et al., 2017). Another critical gap is the integration of LCA and LCC. While environmental assessments are relatively mature, economic evaluations are often partial, focusing only on direct operational and investment costs. Shared infrastructure and avoided costs are rarely treated consistently across actors. Recent advances address this by developing matrix-based unified models such as UM3-LCE3-ISN, which allow the simultaneous treatment of environmental and cost flows (Kerdlap et al., 2020), or by combining Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA) with Cost-Benefit Analysis to capture hidden costs and value losses (Leiva et al., 2025).

Preliminary results from the s-LCA review reveal additional challenges and opportunities. Studies show that social dimensions are often underrepresented in industrial symbiosis assessments, with indicators concentrated mainly on job creation, occupational health, and community well-

being. Few analyses systematically capture distributional effects, gender equity, or long-term societal impacts. Moreover, data availability is highly uneven, with most case studies relying on qualitative surveys or secondary reports rather than standardized indicators. These findings highlight the importance of integrating s-LCA into the SYMBA guidelines to ensure that social benefits and risks are evaluated on equal footing with environmental and economic dimensions. By developing clear criteria for selecting indicators and harmonizing them with LCA and LCC frameworks, SYMBA aims to advance a more comprehensive and balanced sustainability assessment of industrial symbiosis.

The mapping exercise identified more than 150 IS solutions implemented across Europe, classified into platforms, approaches, and methodologies. These solutions encompass a broad range of sectors, including wastewater, agri-food, textiles, packaging, and waste valorization, and reflect the diversity of strategies employed to foster circularity and symbiotic exchanges. Geographically, IS initiatives are concentrated in Northern and Western Europe, particularly in Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, the Netherlands, Northern Italy, with emerging clusters in Spain and France. Self-organized networks are particularly prevalent in the Nordic region, while EU-funded methodologies and digital platforms dominate at the continental scale. The collected solutions were then systematically assessed using the MCDA framework. The final evaluation integrated perspectives from external stakeholders through surveys and co-creation workshops. The consolidated weighting factors assigned the highest importance to SymRL (28%), followed by ERL (22%), with ORL and LRL equally weighted (18%) and SRL ranked lowest (14%). This distribution reflects a consensus that technical and environmental feasibility are the most decisive factor for implementing IS.

5. Conclusions

This paper highlights how advancing industrial symbiosis represents a joint exercise between robust policy frameworks, methodological innovation, and the deployment of practical implementation tools. Through the SYMBA project, a comprehensive framework is being developed that combines evidence-based guidelines, a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) tool, and real-world testing in diverse European demo regions. This integrated approach not only identifies barriers and opportunities but also provides concrete solutions for strengthening industrial cooperation across the textile, waste, wastewater, packaging, and agri-food sectors.

By bridging scientific methods and policy action, SYMBA creates a structured pathway that aligns regional practices with the broader objectives of the circular and bio-based economy. The co-creation of tools with stakeholders ensures that the developed methodologies are both scientifically sound and practically relevant, addressing the specific needs and constraints of local industrial ecosystems. This participatory dimension reinforces stakeholder ownership and facilitates long-term adoption beyond the project's lifetime.

The project's emphasis on scalability and transferability underlines its potential to serve as a reference model for future initiatives. Through harmonized guidelines on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA), SYMBA contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the environmental, economic, and social impacts of symbiotic exchanges. The integration of these tools enables industries to quantify benefits, reduce uncertainties, and make informed decisions that balance performance with sustainability. In addition, the policy insights generated through SYMBA highlight the importance of reducing regulatory complexity, clarifying the status of secondary materials, and enabling open data infrastructures for matchmaking and transparency. Together, these advances form a coherent strategy for embedding industrial symbiosis into European industrial and environmental policies.

Ultimately, SYMBA demonstrates that industrial symbiosis is not merely a technical exercise but a systemic transformation that links innovation, governance, and collaboration. By

pairing methodological rigor with practical implementation, the project paves the way for a new generation of circular industrial ecosystems, ones that optimize resource use, foster regional resilience, and accelerate Europe's transition toward a sustainable, climate-neutral, and inclusive economy.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. 101135562. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

References

- Aissani L., Le Féon S., Lacassagne A., Bahers J.-B., (2019), Life cycle assessment of industrial symbiosis: A critical review of relevant reference scenarios, *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, **23**, 972–985.
- Belton V., Stewart T., (2002), *Multiple criteria decision analysis: An integrated approach*, Springer, Boston, MA, USA.
- Bocken N.M.P., Short S.W., Rana P., Evans S., (2014), A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, **65**, 42–56.
- Cudecka-Purina N., (2025), Legal barriers and policy gaps in industrial symbiosis: A pathway to regulatory innovation, *Environment. Technology. Resources. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference*, **1**, 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.17770/etr2025vol1.8663>
- Domenech T., Bleischwitz R., Doranova A., Panayotopoulos D., Roman L., (2019), Mapping industrial symbiosis development in Europe: Typologies of networks, characteristics, performance, and contribution to the circular economy, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, **141**, 76–98.
- Dong L., Fujita T., Zhang H., Dai M., Fujii M., Ohnishi S., Geng Y., Liu Z., (2017), Highlighting regional eco-industrial development: Life cycle benefits of an urban industrial symbiosis and implications in China, *Ecological Modelling*, **361**, 164–176.
- Fraccascia L., Giannoccaro I., Albino V., (2019), Business models for industrial symbiosis: A taxonomy focused on the form of governance, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, **146**, 114–126.
- Frosch R.A., Gallopoulos N.E., (1989), Strategies for manufacturing, *Scientific American*, **261**, 144–152.
- Kerdlap P., Low J.S.C., Tan D.Z.L., Yeo Z., Ramakrishna S., (2020), M3-IS-LCA: A methodology for multi-level life cycle environmental performance evaluation of industrial symbiosis networks, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, **161**, 104963, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104963>.
- Leiva H., Julian I., Ventura L., Wallin E., Vendt M., Fornell R., Paniagua F.G., Ascaso S., Gomez-Perez M., (2025), Advancing sustainability through industrial symbiosis: A techno-economic approach using material flow cost accounting and cost-benefit analysis, *Sustainability*, **17**, 2730, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17062730>
- Mattila T., Lehtoranta S., Sokka L., Melanen M., Nissinen A., (2012), Methodological aspects of applying life cycle assessment to industrial symbioses, *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, **16**, 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2011.00443.x>
- Prahalad C.K., Ramaswamy V., (2004), Co-creation experiences: The next practice in value creation, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, **18**, 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dir.20015>
- Sandin G., Peters G.M., (2018), Environmental impact of textile reuse and recycling – A review, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, **184**, 353–365.
- Schaltegger S., Lüdeke-Freund F., Hansen E.G., (2012), Business cases for sustainability: The role of business model innovation for corporate sustainability, *International Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*, **6**, 95–119.
- Sokka L., Lehtoranta S., Nissinen A., Melanen M., (2010), Analyzing the environmental benefits of industrial symbiosis, *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, **15**, 137–155.
- Zhu B., (2013), *Life cycle assessment and simplified life cycle costing on industrial symbiosis*, MSc Thesis, University of Linköping, Sweden.